

Sample Name: dNTPs ATP mix 10uM

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    3
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    3
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 1:14:11 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method         : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                12-20-56\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed   : 12/10/2020 10:10:22 AM by SYSTEM
=====

```



```

=====
Fraction Information
=====

```

```

No Fractions found.
=====

```

```

=====
Area Percent Report
=====

```

```

Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution      :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs

```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	2.162	VB R	0.0746	13.28139	2.64645	0.4637
2	10.509	BV R	0.1887	338.94388	27.54256	11.8336
3	12.981	BV R	0.1738	688.72107	61.07838	24.0453
4	14.819	BB	0.1802	356.18323	30.43626	12.4354
5	16.277	BB	0.1828	762.92413	64.64515	26.6360
6	18.435	BB	0.1883	704.20709	57.96779	24.5860

